

Keynote NFDI4Ing Conference 2022

Unifying the Understanding of RDM in Engineering Science

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Egyptian hieroglyphs

Egyptian Demotic

Ancient Greek

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background: pexels.com
foreground: nypl.getarchive.net

Rosetta Stone

Image: *The Rosetta Stone*, 196 B.C.E., Ptolemaic Period, 112.3 x 75.7 x 28.4 cm, Egypt (British Museum, London) (photo: Steven Zucker, CC BY-NC-SA 2.0)

RDM requires the amalgamation of Engineering and Computer Science

images: pexels.com

Use Case: Ultrashort Pulse Manufacturing

images:
Fraunhofer ILT

The decentralized and adaptive Ultrashort Pulse Manufacturing architecture puts RDM in the spotlight

Complexity

Control and data acquisition is organized in interconnected microservices running on an on-premises *Kubernetes* cluster.

Configurability

Dynamic service deployments enable flexible system reconfigurations.

Observability

Compared to conventional setups, this architecture makes the underlying manufacturing process extremely transparent. However data management becomes challenging.

RDM requires the anticipation of future uses

Use Case: High-Pressure Die Casting

image: Foundry Institute – RWTH Aachen University

image: <https://pixabay.com/photos/crucible-foundry-molten-bronze-2109202/>

Lipp et al. (2021),
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75418-1_3

Creating transparency in High-Pressure Die Casting through digitization

Cloud

Data is collected, stored, made accessible and shared through a *MinIO* object storage running on a *Kubernetes* on-premises cloud infrastructure.

Transport

Node-red and *Apache Kafka* provides easily configurable data streaming, transformation and data model integration. Data flows from machines into the cloud.

Machine

The HPDC unit is digitized through *Internet Protocol*-based *OPC UA* servers using their semantic machine models.

image: Theissen-Lipp et al. (2022). Integrating an XPath-Enhanced OPC UA Data Collection Into Industrial Communication. In 27th IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA) (pre-print). IEEE.

Synergies between academic and industrial research still need to be exploited

Use Case: NFDI4ing Community-based Training

Education

One central common goal of science as well as industry is enabling their people to work with data.

Data Literacy

Being able to read, understand, create and communicate data as information.

Trainings

Creating and sharing trainings as one way to drive the community forward.

Example: Research Methods in Engineering Science

Methods A common goal of academic and industrial research is the development and establishment of new data management methods for various domains.

Science		Industry
One-of-a-kind experiments	Unique Experiments	R&D department
Research software development, e.g. AR for manufacturing	Software Development	Industrial software products
Data publishing and unique identifier, e.g. DOI & ORCID	Data Lineage and Provenance	Product tracking and traceability

Computer vision, archiving solutions	High-performance Computing	Recommendations systems and machine learning services
Multi-scale material simulations	Simulation	Car crash simulations, NVH simulation and CFD
Many heterogeneous data sources, Shibboleth and single-sign-on	Data Access Management	Data sharing and access for reporting and product development
Digital twins and digital shadows	Quality Assurance & Control	Product / Process Quality, ISO 9000

Unifying the Understanding of Research Data Management

Successful research data management requires methods of both disciplines, engineering science and computer science to be combined.

Research data management does not only need represent the current state of the art, but must also reflect, envision and help to shape future technologies and domains of application.

Research is not only conducted at universities. Finding and exploiting areas of cooperation and synergy is essential to reach an integrated vision of research data management.

NFDI4Ing: A strongly integrated and coherent team

7 Archetypes
7 Base Services
5 Community
Clusters

4 + 1 Sections

● Thank you for listening!

Image: The Rosetta Stone, 196 B.C.E., Ptolemaic Period, 112.3 x 75.7 x 28.4 cm, Egypt (British Museum, London) (photo: Steven Zucker, CC BY-NC-SA 2.0)

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